

The Influence of Service Quality on Visitor Satisfaction at Kurenai Beach Tourism

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of service quality on visitor satisfaction at Kurenai Beach Tourism. This study aims to determine whether the effect of service quality on visitor satisfaction is seen from the quality of the product and the quality of service provided by Kurenai Beach tourism officers. This type of research uses a quantitative approach. The type of data used is primary data obtained through observations / observations on the working time of workers at Kurenai Beach tourism and secondary data obtained from data on the number of visitors at Kurenai Beach tourist attraction.

The results showed that visitor satisfaction was more influenced by other variables. This is only natural, because judging from the magnitude of the correlation coefficient between variables shows there is significance.

Keywords: Service Quality, Visitor Satisfaction

1. Introduction

Tourism is a very reliable field because it can provide and increase regional income. This is evident from the increasing number of new tourist attractions that have sprung up both in terms of relatively affordable prices, to moderate and even at quite expensive rates.

Indonesia is a country with many islands and a tropical climate, where there are tons of attractions ranging from nature tourism, playgrounds and many more. But to support the tourism sector, it takes elements that are closely related in terms of helping the growth and progress of the tourism world.

The development of the business world is now increasingly dynamic along with the increasing public demand for products and services to meet all their needs. In order to maintain business continuity in the midst of highly competitive business competition, a company must provide customer satisfaction by talking outside the main tasks and functions, playing cell phones or watching TV.

The development of economic activities always has an influence on the marketing aspect. Company management is required to have the right marketing concept in order to always be able to overcome competition in the business world. In general, every company adheres to a consumer-oriented marketing system, namely a marketing system that always strives to meet the needs and desires of consumers. In its development, the tourism sector plays an important role in supporting the growth of the national economy because its existence can contribute to the country's foreign exchange earnings, expand employment opportunities, and introduce national culture so that it should be developed.

The focus on building relationship with customers rather than just focusing on transactions is changing how businesses interact with their customers. The number of available choices to customers has grown in recent years. In order to increase the value of the customer asset over time, customer relationship management places an emphasis on two-way communication between suppliers and customers.

Two (2) main factors affect service quality, namely expected service and perceived service. If the service received (perceived service) is in accordance with what consumers expect (expected service), then the quality of the service concerned will be considered good. If the service received (perceived service) exceeds the expected service, then the service quality is perceived as ideal quality. Conversely, if the service received (perceived service) is worse than the expected service, then the service quality is perceived as poor. Tourism objects are service products offered by a service company with the hope that consumers will come to visit and enjoy the tourist objects offered. To be able to attract customer satisfaction, managers must be able to provide the best quality of service to create customer satisfaction [5].

Of the many tourist attractions in Gorontalo, one of the favorite destinations for families is the beach. In Botubarani, precisely in Kabila Bone sub-district, Bone Bolango district, Gorontalo province, there is one of the family's favorite recreational spots, Kurenai beach. Based on observations made by researchers related to the problems in this study, namely, the current conditions at Kurenai Beach tourism are still not in accordance with what visitors expect because there are still some visitors who feel less satisfied with the services at Kurenai beach, the cleanliness of the beach is not maintained causing there is still garbage scattered around the beach area and the lack of supporting facilities such as bathrooms and toilets.

Definition of Human Resources Management

Human resources management is a series of organizational activities directed at attracting, developing, and retaining an effective workforce. In addition) Human Resource Management (HRM) is: "The activities of planning, procuring, developing, maintaining, and using human resources to achieve both individual and organizational goals." [4]

Human resource management is "the science and art of managing the relationship and role of labor so that it effectively and efficiently helps realize the goals of the company, employees, and society" [6]. Human Resource Management (HRM) is: "The process of managing people, through planning, recruitment, selection, training, development, compensation, career, safety and health and maintaining industrial relations until termination of employment in order to achieve company goals and improve stakeholder welfare." [7].

"Human resource management, abbreviated as HRM, is a science or a way of how to manage the relationship and role of resources (labor) owned by individuals efficiently and effectively and can be used optimally so that the common goals of the company, employees and society are maximized."

1) Functions of Human Resource Management

The functions of human resource management are as follows:

1. Managerial function

a) Planning (planning)

Planning is the process of determining goals and guidelines for implementation by choosing the best of the available alternatives. Planning in the HRM process is the recruitment of the workforce needed by the company.

b) Organizing

Organizing is defined as a process of determining, grouping, and arranging the various activities needed to achieve goals. Organizing can be done by placing employees according to their areas of expertise and providing the tools needed by employees to support their work.

c) Supervision (controlling)

Supervision (controlling)

Supervision is the process of regulating various factors in the company so that they are in accordance with the accuracy of the plan. Supervision is defined as the process of monitoring activities; the aim is to determine the expectations that will be achieved and to correct deviations that occur. The expectations in question are the goals that have been set to be achieved and the programs that have been planned to be carried out within a certain period. The main purpose of supervision is to try to make what is planned come true. With thorough supervision, it will be easier for an agency to analyze the obstacles that arise in management. Thus, the solution to the problems that arise will be taken wisely.

d) Motivation

Motivation is a characteristic of human psychology that contributes to a person's level of commitment. Motivation includes factors that cause, channel, and maintain human behavior in the direction of a certain determination. Motivation can also be interpreted as providing driving force that creates work enthusiasm for someone to want to work together, work effectively and be integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. Basically, companies not only expect capable, capable, and skilled employees, but most importantly they want to work hard and want to achieve optimal work results.

e) Evaluation

Evaluation or also called control is a reporting system activity that is compatible with the overall reporting structure, develops standards of behavior, measures results based on desired quality in relation to goals, takes corrective action, and provides rewards. With the evaluation carried out by the company, it can measure the success rate of an organization.

2) HRM Objectives

The objectives of HRM are as follows:

- a) Determine the quality and quantity of employees who will fill all positions within the company.
 - b) Ensure the availability of present and future labor, so that every job is done.
 - c) Avoid mismanagement and overlap in the implementation of tasks.
 - d) Facilitate coordination, integration, and synchronization (KIS) so that work productivity increases.
 - e) Avoid employee shortages and excesses
 - f) To be a guideline in determining employee attraction, selection, development, compensation, integration, maintenance, discipline, and dismissal programs.
 - g) o be a guideline in carrying out mutations (vertical or horizontal).
 - h) Become the basis for employee appraisal.
- 3) Service Quality
- According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI) service is helping to prepare (take care of) what someone needs.
- According to Kotler in Hendro and Syamswana (2017) the definition of service is any action or activity that can be offered by a party to another party, which is basically intangible and does not result in any ownership.
- Service quality is the whole of the features and characteristics of a product or service that support its ability to satisfy needs directly or indirectly [9]. So, service quality is an interaction between customers and employees whose results can be directly felt by customers at that time.
- a) Service Quality Indicators
- There are five dimensions of service that are often used to measure service quality. The five dimensions are as follows:
1. Reliability, namely the ability to provide the desired service immediately, accurately and satisfactorily. Performance must be in accordance with customer expectations which means timeliness, the same service for all customers without any errors, sympathetic attitude and high accuracy.
 2. Responsiveness, namely the company's ability to help and provide fast (responsive) and precise service to customers with clear information delivery. Letting customers wait without a clear reason causes a negative perception of service quality.
 3. Assurance, the existence of certainty, namely the knowledge, courtesy and ability of employees to foster customer confidence in the services provided.
 4. Empathy, which is providing sincere and individual or personal attention given to customers by trying to understand consumer desires. Where a company is expected to have an understanding and knowledge of customers, understand specific customer needs, and have a convenient organizing time for customers.
 5. Tangibles (physical evidence), namely the ability of a company to show its existence to external parties of the company. The appearance and ability of the company's physical facilities and infrastructure and the surrounding environment are tangible evidence of the services provided by the company.
- 4) Service Quality Gap

The dimensions of service quality that have been mentioned must be combined properly because if not, this can cause a gap between the company and the customer [10]. Customer-perceived quality in the service industry, identifies five gaps that cause service delivery failures, namely:

a. Management perception gap

This gap occurs due to a lack of marketing research orientation, inadequate utilization of research findings, lack of interaction between management and customers, inadequate bottom-up communication, and too many levels of management.

b. Quality specification gap Namely the gap between management's perception of service user expectations and service quality specifications. Gaps occur, among others, due to insufficient management commitment to service quality, perceptions of infeasibility, insufficient standardization of tasks, and lack of goal setting.

c. Service delivery gap

This gap is caused by the following factors:

- 1) Role ambiguity is the extent to which employees can perform tasks in accordance with manager expectations but satisfy customers,
- 2) Role conflict is the extent to which employees believe they are not satisfying all parties.
- 3) the suitability of employees with the tasks they have to do.
- 4) kesesuaian teknologi yang digunakan pegawai.
- 5) the suitability of the technology used by employees. control system from superiors, namely the inadequacy of the appraisal system and the reward system,
- 6) perceived control, namely the extent to which employees feel freedom or flexibility to determine the way of service.
- 7) team work, namely the extent to which employees and management formulate common goals in satisfying customers together and integrated.

d. Marketing communication gap

This gap occurs because:

- 1) inadequate horizontal communication.
- 2) there is a tendency to over-promise. What the company faces is if the promises made cannot be fulfilled.

e. Gaps in perceived service

Namely the difference in perceptions between services perceived and expected by customers. If both prove to be the same, the company will get a positive image and impact. However, if what is received is lower than expected, then this gap will cause problems for the company.

5) Visitor or Customer Satisfaction

Satisfaction or satisfaction from Latin "satis" (meaning good enough) and "facto" (doing or making) thus satisfaction can be interpreted as the fulfillment of something or something adequate. Meanwhile, in terms of satisfaction, satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises from comparing the perceived performance of a product (or result) against their expectations. If performance fails to meet expectations, the customer will be dissatisfied. If performance matches

expectations, the customer will be satisfied. If the performance exceeds expectations, the customer will be very satisfied or happy. Visitor satisfaction is the customer's response to the evaluation of the difference in initial expectations before purchase and the actual performance of the product or service as perceived after the service. In the context of tourism, visitor satisfaction is the result of an evaluation after someone visits a destination by comparing reality and desired expectations. Customer satisfaction is an assessment of the customer's use of goods or services based on expectations and reality [3]. Customer satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises from comparing the product's perceived performance (or results) against their expectations.

a. Factors Affecting Visitor or Customer (traveler) Satisfaction

Five main factors that need to be considered in relation to customer satisfaction include:

- 1) Quality of Tourism Products Consumers will be satisfied if the results of their evaluation show that the products they use are of high quality. A product is said to be of quality for someone, if the product can fulfill their needs. There are two types of product quality, namely external and internal. One of the product qualities of external factors is the brand image perceived by tourists.
- 2) Quality of Tourist Services Consumers will feel satisfied if they get good service or in accordance with expectations.
- 3) Emotional Image Is the emotional state of a consumer in the form of feelings of pleasure, pride or satisfaction.
- 4) Price Products that have the same quality but set a relatively low price will provide higher value.
- 5) Cost Consumers who do not need to pay additional costs or do not need to waste time getting a product or service tend to be satisfied with the product or service. [8]

b. Indicators of Consumer Satisfaction (Tourists)

- 1) Tourist involvement in evaluating various factors that will significantly affect their satisfaction. These factors are: The hospitality of the local community (host) and the attitude of employees towards tourists. Tourist satisfaction does not only come from beautiful destinations, but also from their encounters with local communities and employees of tourism service providers. Negative host perceptions of tourists can trigger dissatisfaction and deter tourists from returning. Conversely, positive host perceptions can motivate tourists to visit the same destination in the future.
- 2) Service quality relating to politeness, friendliness, efficiency, and responsiveness of service personnel to tourist requests and complaints.
- 3) Accommodation and facilities as a significant factor affecting tourist satisfaction, both physically and psychologically.
- 4) The culture of tourism product consumption behavior is seen as a pluralistic, integrative, and multidimensional social phenomenon. One aspect of culture, such as language, can help facilitate communication between the host and guest and promote the destination as a better place to visit.

- 5) Price (monetary cost) which relates to assessing traveler satisfaction and not knowing whether other destinations' offerings can be exceptional. The performance of tourism dimensions that are rated the same as other destinations (e.g. food quality, service quality, safety, water, sports, comfort, and entertainment) can be both a threat and an opportunity for the company, in the long run, competitive ability may become difficult, unless the destination authority seeks to maintain and improve its destination performance to create clearer differentiation.
- 6) Non-monetary costs. In tourism, the perception of non-monetary costs (in addition to reasonable monetary costs), inherent in-service quality, emotional response, and reputation can extend the vacation period, and are likely to be important determinants of future behavior and intentions.

2. Methods

The research method used in this study is descriptive quantitative. Data obtained from data collection will then be analyzed univariately. Univariate analysis is used because the data contains only two variables and does not relate to cause or effect relationships. The purpose of univariate analysis is to describe the data simply to find patterns in the data. This type of research is associative research, which is research that aims to determine the effect or relationship between two or more variables. This study is to determine the effect of service quality (X) on visitor satisfaction (Y) at Kurenai Beach tourist attraction, the population and sample in this study were all visitors to Kurenai Beach tourist attraction totaling 30 people. The sample size is obtained through calculation with the following formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + (N \times e^2)}$$
$$n = \frac{310}{1 + (310 \times 10\%^2)}$$
$$= 75,61$$

So based on the above results, the sample taken for this study was 76 respondents with an error rate of 10%.

3. Results

This research was conducted from September 2022 to November 2022 Completed.

Table 4.1. Research Instrument Validation Test

Variabel	Indikator	Item	Korelasi	Kesimpulan
Kualitas Pelayanan (X)	Reliability (X.1)	X111	1.000	Valid
		X112	0.920	Valid
		X113	0.888	Valid
		X114	0.906	Valid
	Responstveness (X.2)	X121	0.892	Valid
		X122	0.956	Valid
		X123	0.941	Valid
		X124	0.941	Valid
	Assurance (X.3)	X131	1.000	Valid
		X132	0.920	Valid
		X133	0.888	Valid
		X134	0.906	Valid
	Empathy (X.4)	X141	1.000	Valid
		X142	0.920	Valid
X143		0.888	Valid	
X144		0.906	Valid	
Tangibles (X.5)	X211	0.953	Valid	
	X212	0.939	Valid	
	X213	0.926	Valid	
	X214	0.953	Valid	
Kepuasan Pengunjung (Y)	Kualitas produk (Y1)	Y11	0.920	Valid
		Y12	1.000	Valid
		Y13	0.920	Valid
		Y14	0.953	Valid
	Kualitas Pelayanan (Y2)	Y21	0.926	Valid
		Y22	0.888	
		Y23	0.920	
		Y24	0.953	
		Y25	0.888	
		Y26	0.920	
		Y27	0.920	
		Y28	0.888	
		Y29	0.927	
		Y30	0.926	
Y31		0.926		
Y32		0.920		
Y33		0.926		

Variabel	Indikator	Item	Korelasi	Kesimpulan
		Y34	0.920	
		Y35	0.923	
		Y36	0.888	
		Y37	0.926	
		Y38	1.000	
		Y39	0.920	
		Y40	0.888	
		Y41	0.926	
		Y42	0.926	
		Y43	0.888	
		Y45	0.920	
		Y46	0.888	
		Y47	0.924	
		Y48	0.920	
		Y49	1.000	
		Y50	0.888	

Source: Processed Data 2022

Table 4.1 above shows the correlation value of all question items on the questionnaire for all indicators and items is above 0.3. Thus, it can be concluded that all items have met the validity. The next stage is presented testing the reliability of the instrument. The instrument is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha value is > 0.6. Complete results are presented in Appendix 3, and summarized in the following table.

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	20.7279	40.5726	32.3696	7.15776	76
Residual	-1.13787	1.74958	.00000	.58139	76
Std. Predicted Value	-1.626	1.146	.000	1.000	76
Std. Residual	-1.891	2.907	.000	.966	76

The Residuals Statistics results obtained a Std Deviation value of .58139 with an N value of 76. Thus the dependent variable y or residuals meets the criteria.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		76
Normal	Mean	.0000000
Parameters ^{a,b}	Std. Deviation	.58139393
Most	Absolute	.187
Extreme	Positive	.168
Differences	Negative	-.187
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		4.269
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.080

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

The analysis results show that the data is normally distributed, this can be seen from the KolmogorovSmirnov test, as well as the probability number or Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.080. This means that the significance value or probability value is more than 0.05 the data distribution is normal.

Scatterplot

The Normal P-P Plot Of Regression Standardized Residual results show that the plotting points in the picture above always follow and approach the diagonal line. Therefore, as a

basis or guideline for decision making in the probability plot technique normality test, it can be concluded that the residual value is normally distributed. Thus, the normalization assumption for the residual value in the simple linear regression analysis in this study can be fulfilled.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95,0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	.856	.413		2.074	.044	.023	1.689
x1	.399	.280	.553	3.731	.001	.461	.137

a. Dependent Variable: X

From the output above, it is known that the significance value of the financing variable (X) is 0.44 > 0.05, meaning that the significance value or probability value is more than 0.05, the data distribution is normal.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.497 ^a	.593	.593	.30280	.593	1021.472	1	75	.000	1.029

a. Dependent Variable: Y

The table above explains the percentage of the influence of the independent variable or predictor variable on the dependent variable. The magnitude of the coefficient of determination is 0.593, which means that the influence of the independent variable (independent) is 59.3%. While 40.7% (100%-59.3%) is influenced by other variables. So the effect of Service Quality on Visitor Satisfaction is only 59.3% while the influence of other variables is 40.7%. Thus, it means that Visitor Satisfaction is still influenced by other variables. This is only natural, because judging from the magnitude of the correlation coefficient between variables, it shows that there is significance.

4. Discussion

Based on the results of the study, it shows that simultaneously tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy contribute significantly to visitor satisfaction with an influence of 59.7%. The form of contribution between tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy to visitor satisfaction is a positive influence indicated by the prices of the regression coefficients which are positive. Thus, it can be explained that if the variables of tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy are increased together, it will be followed by an

increase in visitor satisfaction and vice versa if the variables of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy decrease together, it will be followed by a decrease in visitor satisfaction. Partially tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy have a significant effect on visitor satisfaction and for more details will be detailed as follows:

The Effect of Tangibles (Direct Evidence) on Visitor Satisfaction. Tangibles (direct evidence) partially contributed to visitor satisfaction by 2.5%. From the research results it was revealed that 68 70.34% of respondents stated that the tangibles (direct evidence) applied by Kurenai Beach were in the good category, at Kurenai Beach they had implemented direct evidence which included, physical facilities, parking lots and the appearance of good workers so that visitors were satisfied with the facilities provided. The embodiment or physical evidence of services, equipment facilities used and other physical representations affect service user satisfaction [10]. However, the contribution caused is relatively small, namely (2.5%), even though the tangibles (direct evidence) on Kurenai Beach are good, this happens because in making visits the visitors do not always pay attention to the tangibles (direct evidence) applied by Kurenai Beach.

The Effect of Reliability on Visitor Satisfaction Reliability partially contributes to visitor satisfaction by 1.25%. From the research results it was revealed that 69.57% of respondents stated that the reliability applied by Kurenai Beach was in the good category, seen from the application of reliability aspects such as the accuracy of service to visitors who need help. Kurenai Beach focuses on effective service aspects so that visitors are satisfied with the reliability that has been implemented by the manager. This is in accordance with the theory that reliability which includes two main things, namely work consistency (performance) and the ability to be trusted (dependability) important factors that affect service life [10]. However, the contribution caused is very small, namely (1.25%) even though the reliability at Kurenai Beach is good, this happens because in making visits the visitors to Kurenai Beach do not always pay attention to the reliability.

The Effect of Responsiveness on Visitor Satisfaction Responsiveness partially contributes to visitor satisfaction with the greatest influence among other variables, namely 7.13%. From the research results, it was revealed that 71.39% of respondents stated that the responsiveness applied by Kurenai Beach was in the good category. Kurenai Beach has implemented the responsiveness aspect well which focuses on providing services quickly and the desire of workers to help visitors if they experience problems or need help. This is in accordance with the theory which states that in service marketing there are five important variables that need to be considered in improving service quality, one of which is the responsiveness variable [10]. The main factor determining customer satisfaction is customer perception of service quality [10]. However, the contribution caused by the small relative is (7.13%) even though the responsiveness at Kurenai Beach is good, this happens because in making visits the visitors to Kurenai Beach do not always pay attention to the responsiveness.

The Effect of Assurance on Visitor Satisfaction Assurance partially contributes to visitor satisfaction with an influence of 1.3%. From the research results it was revealed that 80.50% of respondents stated that the assurance applied by Kurenai Beach was in the good category. This is because Kurenai Beach has implemented assurance which focuses on assurance regarding the friendliness and politeness of workers in providing services to

visitors, the safety of recreational parks which includes the safety of visitors and the security of parking lots, as well as workers' knowledge of the situation of recreational parks. This is in accordance with the theory that assurance is one aspect of service quality that affects visitor satisfaction [10].

The influence caused is relatively small, namely (1.3%) even though the assurance at Kurenai Beach is good, this happens because in making visits the visitors to Kurenai Beach do not pay too much attention to the assurance aspect. The Effect of Empathy (Empathy) on Visitor Satisfaction Empathy (empathy) partially contributes to visitor satisfaction with an influence of 1.14%. From the research results, it was revealed that 69.92% of respondents stated that the empathy applied by Kurenai Beach was in the good category. In implementing the empathy aspect, Kurenai Beach focuses more on good communication with visitors so that visitors feel more respected and valued. The creation of good communication will provide information to the management so that it can understand the needs of visitors so as to create visitor satisfaction, empathy is one of the service quality variables that affect customer satisfaction [10]. In a service business, service quality plays an important role in explaining whether or not service consumers are satisfied [10]. But the effect caused is small, namely (1.14%) even though the empathy on Kurenai Beach is already in the good category, this happens because in making visits the visitors to Kurenai Beach do not pay too much attention to the empathy aspect (empathy). Meanwhile, seen from the determination test, the percentage of the influence of the independent variable or predictor variable on the dependent variable shows that the coefficient of determination is 0.593, which means that the influence of the independent variable is 59.3%. While 40.7% (100%-59.3%) is influenced by other variables. So, the effect of Service Quality on Visitor Satisfaction is only 59.3% while the influence of other variables is 40.7%. Thus, it means that Visitor Satisfaction is still influenced by other variables. This is only natural, because judging from the magnitude of the correlation coefficient between variables, it shows that there is significance.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the results of the research on the Effect of Service Quality on Visitor Satisfaction at Kurenai Beach Tourism, researchers can conclude that service quality has a significant effect on visitor loyalty at Kurenai Beach Tourism with several indicators, namely:

1) Level of service quality

The form of contribution between tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy to visitor satisfaction is a positive influence indicated by the prices of the regression coefficients which are positive. Thus, it can be explained that if the variables of tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy are increased together, it will be followed by an increase in visitor satisfaction and vice versa if the variables of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy decrease together, it will be followed by a decrease in visitor satisfaction. Partially tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy have a significant effect on visitor satisfaction.

2) Level of Visitor Satisfaction

The coefficient of determination is 0.593, which means that the effect of independent variables is 59.3%. While 40.7% (100%-59.3%) is influenced by other variables. So, the effect of Service Quality on Visitor Satisfaction is only 59.3% while the influence of other variables is 40.7%. Thus, it means that Visitor Satisfaction is greater influenced by other variables. This is only natural, because judging from the magnitude of the correlation coefficient between variables, it shows that there is significance.

The mechanism of how recreation experiences lead to attitude and behavior change is a complex system involving satisfaction, knowledge, place attachment, environmental commitment, and perceived value of destinations. In terms of loyalty, satisfaction positively influences visitors' intentions to revisit, or to recommend a visit to others. Length of stay also appeared to be positively associated with visitor loyalty, which is likely mediated by satisfaction. Visitors who spend more days to stay have more time and opportunities to explore and enjoy the view of Kurenai Beach and likely have higher satisfaction.

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